

Demonstrating the feasibility of a CTI mitigation strategy for astrometry using astrometric sky-like test data

L. Lindegren

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ABSTRACT. A strategy is proposed for demonstrating the feasibility of CTI mitigation in the astrometric data processing, using CCD test data with the sky-like mask. The idea is to process several test datasets together in an AGIS-like least-squares solution, and calculate statistics of the positional residuals. The demonstration is deemed a success if the residuals in the irradiated part of the CCD are not increased by more than TBD percent, compared with the residuals in the non-irradiated part, which in turn should be consistent with expected error levels from the photon statistics and readout noise.

1 Introduction

This note deals with the problem how we can provide, to ourselves and to the outside world, a simple and convincing demonstration that the positional biases caused by the expected radiation damage of Gaia's astrometric CCDs can indeed be managed with the intended strategy, viz., a combination of periodic charge injection and data modelling.¹

The current Astrium approach to the bias calibration [2] is to model the centroid shift as function of (mainly) magnitude and charge injection delay. The required model parameters have to be determined in the astrometric solution (AGIS). A complete demonstration of this approach thus requires both large-scale, realistic simulation of the bias effects and the subsequent processing of these data through the appropriate DPAC chain. This is a huge complication, and it is also to some degree circular, since the simulations must also be based on some (possibly very similar) model of the effects. This model must in turn be verified against test data.

The approach adopted by DPAC is very different, and depends on the accurate calibration of a 'Charge Distortion Model' as part of the data pre-processing (IDT and IDU); thus, ideally, no bias effects are seen in the astrometric solution. This approach is mandatory in order to be able to process arbitrarily complex objects, including multiple stars, solar system objects and the spectra in BP, RP, and RVS. However, to demonstrate the feasibility of this approach will be even more difficult, and perhaps impossible until it is applied on the real mission data.

¹This problem was identified at a meeting of the Gaia Radiation Calibration Working Group in March 2009 [1]. The present note is written in response to Action Item #3 of that meeting.

What is proposed here is a third alternative, which is simple, self-contained, and based on existing test data from the Astrium Radiation Campaign #3 (using the astrometric sky-like mask). Since it uses test data, rather than simulated data, it avoids circularity in the modelling and will be highly realistic. It is formulated in a way which clearly brings out the analogy between the test runs and real Gaia observations: the astrometric parameters, the attitude parameters, and the geometric instrument calibration parameters all have their exact analogues in the test situation. Most importantly, the proposed demonstration should be able to recover the correct ‘astrometric parameters’ (that is, the positions of the holes in the mask), using only data from the damaged part of the CCD, just as Gaia must be able to do its work with only damaged CCDs.

2 The test data

The Astrium Radiation Campaign #3 astrometric test data delivery [3] contains many datasets with multiple runs of the sky-like mask across the irradiated zone of the CCD (in two different AC positions, ZI1 and ZI2) as well as the non-irradiated zone (ZNI), in all cases with the mask both in the normal position (‘mask up’) and rotated 180° (‘mask down’). The mask contains 1413 holes (subsequently referred to as ‘stars’), 600 of them in a regular pattern on either side of the pseudo-random part (with 813 stars covering a certain magnitude range). Reduced illumination levels were used in some datasets, simulating sky areas with a reduced density of stars.

For a valid demonstration, it must be possible to determine the ‘undamaged’ star positions exclusively from ‘damaged’ data (i.e., without using the ZNI runs). This is in principle possible thanks to measurements being made both in the ‘mask up’ and ‘mask down’ configurations, since the positional bias due to the CTI has opposite signs (relative to the mask) in the two cases. In the real mission, the corresponding situation occurs when the same great-circle strip of the sky is scanned in opposite directions, which happens many times per year at intervals of a few months.

3 Observation model

In the following, index i is always used to identify the stars on the mask (whether regular or sky-like), j identifies a particular dataset, and k the runs within a data set. Thus the double index jk uniquely identifies a run, and ijk a particular observation (i.e., of star i in run jk).

For each star i there is a known nominal position (x_i, y_i) , expressed in samples (including fractions, if necessary), with x reckoned in the AL and y in the AC direction. For practical reasons the origin of x and y should be close to the geometrical centre of the mask. Using the hole positions in the Annex of [3], the nominal positions can be computed as

$$x_i = \text{AL} - 1475, \quad y_i = \text{AC} - 373.3335 \quad (1)$$

Associated with each data set we have $s_j = +1$ if the dataset was taken with ‘mask up’, and $s_j = -1$ for ‘mask down’. Associated with each star/dataset combination there is a certain magnitude of the star, G_{ij} . Associated with each observation there is a known delay between the preceding charge injection (CI) and the observation, denoted T_{ijk} . Moreover, the AC coordinate of the observation on the CCD, m , is also known as function of ijk . All

of these numbers ($x_i, y_i, s_j, G_{ij}, T_{ijk}$, and $m(i, j, k)$) are for the present purposes assumed to be known from the setup of the tests or pre-processing of the data. Note that x_i, y_i are *nominal* coordinates, not the actual (accurate) positions.

Let u_{ijk} be the estimated location of star i in the AL sample stream in run jk . This value should be estimated by Maximum Likelihood fitting to the sample data of a reasonable mean LSF; this procedure will also provide an estimate of the standard error σ_{ijk} of the location (see Sect. 5). The estimated location is modelled as:

$$\begin{aligned}
u_{ijk} - s_j x_i &= s_j \Delta x_i \\
&+ a_{jk}^{(0)} + a_{jk}^{(1)} y_i \\
&+ B(G_{ij}, T_{ijk} | \mathbf{b}) \\
&+ c_j^{(0)} x_i + c_j^{(1)} (x_i^2 - C) + c_j^{(2)} x_i y_i + \dots \\
&+ d_{m(i,j,k)}
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

The unknowns on the right-hand side are:

- Δx_i is the correction to the nominal AL position of star i ;
- $a_{jk}^{(0)}$ and $a_{jk}^{(1)}$ are the ‘attitude’ parameters in run jk , representing the AL origin of the run and a (small) rotation of the mask;
- \mathbf{b} is a parameter vector for the location bias model B (e.g., something like the Astrium CC bias model, but see also Sect. 4);
- $c_j^{(0)}, c_j^{(1)}, \dots$ are ‘large-scale calibration’ parameters in dataset j representing optical distortions that may vary between datasets (C is a constant, equal to the mean value of x_i^2 , making the first two terms approximately orthogonal);
- d_m is the AL offset at AC position m , representing small-scale geometrical shifts in the CCD, including stitching errors. (If full pixel resolution is not needed for this parameter, m could be the integer part of the CCD column index divided by some small integer.)

All of these unknowns have to be determined in a single weighted least-squares solution, using observations from multiple datasets, including in particular scans in both AC positions (ZI1 and ZI2) and in both directions (mask up and down). Thus at least four datasets have to be considered in a single solution. The inclusion of both mask up and down is essential for being able to solve Δx_i ; the inclusion of both ZI1 and ZI2 is essential for being able to solve d_m .

Note that not all the observations should be used in the solution: in principle only the sky-like stars (restriction on i) and the irradiated zone of the CCD (restriction on m) should be included.

A corresponding solution can be made for data in the ZNI by excluding the bias term in (2); this is needed as a reference case for the residual statistics (Sect. 6).²

²Unfortunately there is only one AC position of the mask in ZNI, which could make it difficult to determine d_m uniquely in this case. Further study of this is needed; perhaps the pseudo-solution still provides reliable residual statistics, or additional test runs with a different AC position in the ZNI may ultimately be needed.

The particular model described by (2) implicitly makes a number of assumptions about the properties of the test runs. These have to be examined carefully, and verified by means of the test data, or otherwise modified accordingly. In particular:

1. There is a separate parameter $a_{jk}^{(0)}$ and $a_{jk}^{(1)}$ for each run (jk). This assumes that the translational phasing of the run, and its rotation, are sufficiently variable from one run to the next that they have to be solved for as independent parameters. This is almost certainly true for $a_{jk}^{(0)}$ (translation, which is a first-order effect), but not necessarily for $a_{jk}^{(1)}$ (rotation, which is a higher-order effect). If, for example, the rotation can be considered stable within a dataset (j), then $a_j^{(1)}$ would be the appropriate unknown instead.
2. The large-scale calibration parameters $c_j^{(\cdot)}$ are only needed if there is actually a *variation* of this form between different datasets. If there is just a constant distortion of this form (i.e., the same for all j), then this distortion could just as well be included in Δx_i and we could remove the large-scale calibration terms from the model, as well as the corresponding constraints (5)–(7).

Sufficient knowledge has probably already accumulated from the analysis of the regular mask test data to resolve these issues immediately, subject to verification by the fitting of the model to the data.

4 Degeneracies in the solution

When the normal equations are formed from the observation equations (2), it will be found that the resulting matrix is singular due to multiple degeneracies among the unknowns. For example, adding a constant q to each Δx_i and $s_j q$ to each $a_{jk}^{(0)}$ would obviously leave the right-hand side of (2) unchanged, and therefore cannot be determined from the data. This is not a real problem, however: it just means that the origin of the x axis has not been fixed.³ A simple way to fix the origin is to agree that the true AL star positions should *in the mean* agree with the nominal values x_i . This is tantamount to introducing the constraint on the (unweighted) average of the position corrections:

$$\sum_i \Delta x_i = 0 \quad (3)$$

There is a similar degeneracy between Δx_i and d_m , which could be fixed by the constraint

$$\sum_m d_m = 0 \quad (4)$$

If there are values of m that are not covered by any observation, the corresponding d_m should be removed from the list of unknowns, or constrained to zero.

Each of the large-scale calibration parameters $c_j^{(\cdot)}$ is also degenerate with respect to the Δx_i , in the sense that a linear variation of Δx_i with x_i could also have been represented

³In the real Gaia there is exactly the same degeneracy between the star positions and the attitude, corresponding to the celestial coordinate system being undefined with respect to small rotations about the three axes. This must be fixed by injecting external data in the form of the known positions of a number of quasars.

by a certain offset of $c_j^{(0)}$ for all j , and similarly for the other terms involving $c_j^{(\cdot)}$. These degeneracies can be removed by the additional constraints

$$\sum_i x_i \Delta x_i = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_i (x_i^2 - C) \Delta x_i = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_i x_i y_i \Delta x_i = 0 \quad (7)$$

meaning that the set of position corrections Δx_i should not contain any components that can be interpreted as a second-order distortion.

The bias model $B(G_{ij}, T_{ijk} | \mathbf{b})$ could also have a degeneracy with respect to Δx_i depending on how it is defined. It is recommended that the formulation in terms of the parameters \mathbf{b} is done in such a way that there is no such degeneracy. In practice this means that the condition $B = 0$ should correspond to some particular ‘reference’ situation, e.g., some particular values of G and T . For example, based on the 9-parameter model in [2], Sect. 6.2, the following generalized model could be tried:

$$B(G, T | \mathbf{b}) = \sum_{\substack{\alpha=0 \\ \alpha+\beta>0}}^{N_G-1} \sum_{\beta=0}^{N_T-1} b_{\alpha\beta} (G - G_{\text{ref}})^\alpha \ln^\beta (T/T_{\text{ref}}) \quad (8)$$

depending on the $N_G \times N_T - 1$ parameters $b_{\alpha\beta}$, where G_{ref} and T_{ref} are suitable reference (typical, or average) values for the magnitude and injection delay. Since there is no term for $\alpha = \beta = 0$, the model implies that an object at $G = G_{\text{ref}}$ and $T = T_{\text{ref}}$ has no bias, which effectively defines the zero point for the Δx_i values.

In the above analysis, five constraints have been identified, and it is thus expected that the normal matrix should have a rank defect of exactly five. In fact, the particular linear combinations of the unknowns expressed by the constraints should be null vectors spanning the null space of the normal matrix. Adding the constraints will therefore not in any way ‘force’ or distort the solution.

However, there is in practice no need to explicitly implement these constraints, if the normal equations are solved by SVD, i.e., using the pseudo-inverse of the normal equation. This will provide a valid solution, even if it does not necessarily satisfy the constraints. One should just make sure that the rank of the normals has the expected deficiency (five in the example above), otherwise the solution could have some unpleasant properties.

One concern is that the two AC positions (ZI1 and ZI2) may not be enough to separate Δx_i and d_m . This can be tested rather simply by setting up the normal matrix and making the SVD decomposition. This can be done before any preprocessing is done.

5 Preprocessing

The derivation of u_{ijk} and associated standard errors requires some preprocessing of the sample data not unlike the IDT. The following steps are probably necessary as a minimum:

1. Bias subtraction and conversion to electrons.

2. Location of the CI in the sample stream and estimation of background level as function of T and m .
3. Determination of an approximate, mean LSF. Although the concept of an LSF is doubtful in the presence of CTI effects, the approach to fit a ‘damaged LSF’ is probably good enough for present purposes. The mean LSF could be determined by subtracting the estimated background, finding the centroid (using Tukey’s biweight [4]), normalizing the counts under the profile, superposing many such profiles, and fitting a continuous function to the points.
4. Estimating the location and flux of the image in the sample stream, using the Maximum Likelihood method [5] to fit the mean LSF to the 6–12 central samples, using the previously determined background. The readout noise is also needed. The output is u_{ijk} , a flux estimate and the corresponding formal standard errors.
5. For each dataset, mean fluxes are calculated by averaging over the runs, and converted to magnitudes G_{ij} .

6 Model validation and criterion for successful demonstration

The weighted least-squares fitting minimizes

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{ijk} \left(\frac{u_{ijk}^{\text{obs}} - u_{ijk}^{\text{calc}}}{\sigma_{ijk}} \right)^2 \quad (9)$$

where u_{ijk}^{obs} is the estimated location of the image, u_{ijk}^{calc} the calculated location according to the model (2), and σ_{ijk} the formal standard error of the location estimate. For a good fit, one expects χ^2 to be approximately equal to the number of degrees of freedom, $\nu = n_{\text{obs}} - n_{\text{par}} + n_{\text{con}}$ depending on the number of observations, number of parameters (unknowns) fitted, and number of constraints ($n_{\text{par}} - n_{\text{con}}$ should equal the rank of the normal matrix). Because ν will be quite large (of order 10^5 – 10^7) one expects in fact that the unit weight error $U = \sqrt{\chi^2/\nu} \simeq 1$. A value significantly greater than 1.0 would indicate that the model needs to be improved.

Let U_{ZI} be the unit weight error obtained from the solution using ZI1 and ZI2 data, and U_{ZNI} the same statistics from the ZNI data (but without bias term). The demonstration could be deemed successful if both the following conditions are satisfied:

$$U_{\text{ZNI}} \leq 1 + \epsilon_0, \quad U_{\text{ZI}} \leq (1 + \epsilon_1)U_{\text{ZNI}} \quad (10)$$

where ϵ_0 and ϵ_1 are numbers to be defined (probably of order 5–20%). The first condition ensures that the test setup is stable enough, and the adopted observation model accurate enough to be able to provide a valid demonstration. The second condition ensures that the bias model is able to remove the CTI effect to a sufficient degree.

Much more detailed information can of course be derived from the statistics, e.g., on the accuracy of the bias correction (in μas) as function of magnitude and other conditions (time since CI, presence of polluting stars, etc) of relevance for the accuracy analysis.

References

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